

THE HISTORY OF THE CONCEPT OF PRECEDENCE ON THE MATERIAL OF RUSSIAN UZBEK STUDIES

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Annotation. It is known that the Uzbek people have been in economic, political and cultural relations with other peoples throughout the historical periods. These contacts have a certain influence on the language of the people with whom they interact. As a result of interaction, changes occur in all sections of the language: phonetics, lexis, grammar, etc. Change and development in the language is strong in the lexicon of the language. This article discusses this.

Key words. Internationalization, Russian-international, Central Asia, A.I. Gersen, phonetics, lexicon, grammar.

It is known that the Uzbek people have been in economic, political and cultural relations with other peoples throughout the historical periods. These contacts have a certain influence on the language of the people with whom they interact. As a result of interaction, changes occur in all sections of the language: phonetics, lexis, grammar, etc. Change and development in the language is strong in the lexicon of the language.

"Russia and Uzbekistan are closely related to each other by common history and cultural heritage. I myself graduated from a Russian-language school, so I am very pleased to support such a long-term and strategic initiative of the Government of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation to teach the Russian language in my homeland. I am convinced that this is not only about supporting education, but also about supporting our common traditions and talents. This initiative will be successful and will be well received by the entire population of Uzbekistan, so I wish it great success," said Alisher Usmanov.

Russian-international words. From the second half of the 19th century, Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, became a colonial country of Tsarist Russia. The influence of the Russian language on the Uzbek language began from this period. Many words have changed from the Russian language and from other languages through the Russian language.

The introduction of words into the Uzbek language from the Russian language and through the Russian language from the languages of the European nations (French, Italian, German, English, Spanish) includes two historical periods:

1. The period from the second half of the 19th century to the beginning of the 20th century.
2. The period after 1917.

Words from the Russian language changed in two ways:

1. Russian workers, foremen, Russian soldiers, officials with different types of communication with the local population through oral speech: chilon (chlen), adbakat (lawyer), apisor (officer), iskalat (sklad), akhran (okhrana), choynai (kettle) like.
2. Through the press: ayrapilan (aeroplane), factory (factory), poshta (post office), zovut (factory), uez (uezd), kridit (credit), banka (bank), bill of exchange (promissory note).

Some of the words that entered through the Russian language are international words that are used in the languages of many peoples of the world almost without changing the sound side. They are usually called international words.

The official representative of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Russia, Maria Zakharova, expressed her opinion on the role of the Russian language in Uzbekistan in her traditional briefing. According to him, it is important that in the new legislation adopted in Uzbekistan, the norms on language discrimination are not allowed.

"On January 27, Uzbekistan adopted the first reading of the draft law "On amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Language".

It should be noted that it reflects the status of other languages (about 100 people live in the republic) and non-discrimination based on language symbols.

We are implementing a number of joint educational projects aimed at strengthening knowledge of the Russian language in Uzbekistan. It (the Russian language) is second only to the state language in terms of distribution and social importance, and it is mandatory to learn it in secondary schools in Uzbekistan," says Zakharova.

He noted that the decision to establish a branch of the Russian State Pedagogical University named after A.I. Gersen in Tashkent by the leadership of the Republic in October 2020 is an important step in the development of cooperation.

"In addition to training bachelor's and master's degrees, he is also engaged in professional retraining of pedagogues, who are said to be lacking by our partners. Today, their number in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan is about 1,000," says the representative of the RF MFA.

In October 2020, Zakharova studied at the Russian State Pedagogical University named after A.I. Gersen with the support of Alisher Usmanov's "Art, Science and Sport" charity fund by the Ministry of Education of Russia and the Ministry of Public Education of Uzbekistan. He also mentioned the launch of a project until 2030 to improve the quality of teaching Russian language and general education subjects in Russian.

It is known that in 2020-2030, 14 regional centers and up to 10,000 schools in the country will be gradually set up to send up to a thousand Russian specialists to the republic, improve the qualifications of pedagogues in the public education system of Uzbekistan and retrain them. phase coverage is planned.

Let us remind you that Maria Zakharova made a statement about the language policy in Uzbekistan, especially the Uzbek language, in May of last year. The representative of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs commented on the draft decision on the mandatory use of the national language in the state agencies of Uzbekistan and said that there are not many supporters of this proposal.

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